

Original paper

Floristic diversity of the central part of the South Bačka loess terrace (Vojvodina, Serbia)

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Summary: Three year-long botanical field investigations of the central part of the South Bačka loess terrace were conducted with the purpose to determine the floristic diversity of this primarily agricultural area. A total of 518 vascular plant taxa (504 species and 14 subspecies) were registered and classified into 102 families and 316 genera. The families with the most representatives were Asteraceae, Poaceae, Rosaceae, Fabaceae, Lamiaceae, and Brassicaceae, while the most species-rich genera were *Euphorbia*, *Prunus*, *Potentilla*, *Ranunculus*, and *Rumex*. Floral elements were grouped into eight areal types, dominated by the Eurasian areal type. Also, of the 54 noted adventive taxa, 41 had an invasive character. The biological spectrum was characterized by the domination of hemicryptophytes and therophytes. The presence of twenty protected plant species and six tertiary relicts was registered.

Keywords: areal type spectrum, biological spectrum, invasive plant species, loess, South Bačka, vascular flora.

INTRODUCTION

Loess (German *Löss*, meaning loose) is usually defined as terrestrial clastic sediment dominated by silt-sized particles formed by the accumulation of wind-blown dust (Pye 1995). It has been found over a significant fraction of the world (covering approximately 10% of the total land surface), and represents one of the most important pieces of evidence of long-term dust deposition (Marković et al. 2012; Muhs et al. 2014). Loess is predominantly found in the mid-latitude zone of Eurasia, with a maximum thickness of over 100 m recorded in the Loess Plateau of China (Dlussky 2009; Marković et al. 2012). It is also widespread in the Columbia Plateau and Mississippi basin (North America) and on the La Plata basin (South America). Non-typical loess varieties have been noted in some areas of Central Asia, northeastern

Siberia, North Africa, Argentina and New Zealand (Dlussky 2009).

Loess deposits in Vojvodina are among the oldest (dated to the late Early Pleistocene) and best-preserved accumulations in Europe and recent studies have shown that these loess sequences can be directly correlated to the loess records of East Asia (Marković et al. 2012). In the Bačka region of Vojvodina, Bukurov (1975) recognized two types of loess deposits: plateaus (Bačka and Titel loess plateau) and terrace (South Bačka loess terrace). The main difference between these types of loess deposits is the absence of gray zones on loess terraces (Davidović 2005).

For the present study, the investigated area is located in the central part of the South Bačka loess terrace (Fig. 1). It covers the northern part of Bačka Palanka municipality (settlements of Despotovo, Gajdobra, Nova Gajdobra, Piv-

nice, and Silbaš) and the eastern and central parts of Bački Petrovac municipality (settlements Bački Petrovac and Maglič). The central part of the terrace is composed of three loess types – terrestrial, redeposited, and swamp loess (Bukurov 1975). The majority of the investigated area is covered with chernozem-like calcareous meadow soil, with the less frequent presence of chernozem-like limeless meadow soil (Nejgebauer et al. 1972; Radanović 1972; Popov et al. 2016b). Saline soils solonchak (Nejgebauer et al. 1972) and solonetz (Vasin et al. 2010) were also recorded in this area. The main watercourse in this part of the South Bačka loess terrace is the Jegrička river (Bukurov 1975), while the canal network of the Danube-Tisa-Danube (DTD) hydrosystem is also of great importance (Stojanović et al. 2007). The climate is temperate continental with a maximum amount of precipitation in late spring and early summer, along with a secondary maximum in early autumn (Lalić et al. 2011). The indigenous native vegetation of the investigated region is represented by steppe (alliance *Festucion rupicolae* Soó 1940) and forest-steppe communities (alliance *Aceri tatarico-Quercion* Zolyomi et Jakucs 1957) (Stevanović et al. 1995a). Unfortunately, at present, due to the intensification of agriculture and other anthropogenic impacts, this autochthonous vegetation is almost completely devastated. Today only sparse fragments remain, which serve as refugia for steppe plant and animal species (Stevanović et al. 1995a).

Botanical investigations in the Bačka region over the last two and a half centuries have been mainly focused on the specific localities at Subotičko-horgoška sands, Bačka and Titel loess plateaus, salt marshes, and swamps. In contrast, areas that are geomorphologically homogenous, such as loess terraces, were less interesting to botanists, and therefore reduced to sporadic floristic records. The only comprehensive floristic investigation in this part of Bačka was conducted in the northern part of Bačka Palanka, during which 168 taxa of vascular flora were registered (Radonić 1979). In addition to this, individual floristic records were provided by Zorkoczy (1896) for Bačka Palanka, Kupcsok (1914), Prodán (1916), Šajinović (1968) and Anačkov (1997) for Bački Petrovac, whereas Budak (1998) provided an overview of the saline species in the surroundings of Bačka Palanka, Silbaš, and Despotovo. Malidža and Vrbničanin (2006), as well as Radanović et al. (2012) reported the presence of some invasive plant species in the vicinity of Despotovo and Maglič, while Konstantinović and Meseldžija (2004) and Popov et al. (2016a) performed phytocenological studies of the ruderal vegetation in the area of Gajdobra and Silbaš, respectively. Detailed floristic and phytocenological investigations of the aquatic vegetation of the main canal network of the DTD hydrosystem were performed near Bački Petrovac, Nova Gajdobra and Despotovo (Stojanović et al. 2006; Stojanović et

al. 2009; Džigurski et al. 2011), and also along the course of Jegrička river (Lazić et al. 2003; Lazić et al. 2004; Džigurski et al. 2010).

The main aim of the present study was to examine the floristic diversity of the central part of the South Bačka loess terrace and, based on data collected in the field, to perform taxonomic, phytogeographical, and ecological analyses. Additionally, protection and invasive status of some plants have been given.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant material for the present study was collected from 36 localities over a period of three years (2014–2016) representing all vegetation seasons. Plants were herbarized using standard methods (Nikolić 1996) and deposited in the Herbarium collection of the University of Novi Sad (BUNS). Identification of plant material was performed using referent national and regional floras and iconographies (Tutin et al. 1968–1980; Josifović 1972–1977; Jávorka and Csapody 1975; Sarić 1986, 1992; Tutin et al. 1993; Király 2009; Stevanović 2012). Nomenclature was harmonized with reference databases (The Plant List 2013; IPNI 2020), and grouping of angiosperm, fern, horsetail and gymnosperm taxa into higher systematic categories was done in accordance with selected authors (Smith et al. 2006; Takhtajan 2009; Christenhusz et al. 2011). Floral elements were determined according to Gajić (1980) and then classified into defined areal types given by Stevanović (1992a) for the territory of Serbia. Cultivated and ornamental plants were not included in the phytogeographical analysis. Life forms were determined based on Raunkier (1934), modified according to Ellenberg and Mueller-Dombois (1974) and further adapted for the Flora of Serbia by Stevanović (1992b). The protection and invasive status of collected plant taxa was determined in accordance with the “Rules on the protection of strictly protected and protected wild species of plants, animals, and fungi” in the Republic of Serbia (Anonymous 2010a) and according to referral check-lists (Lazarević et al. 2012; Anačkov et al. 2013), respectively.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Floristic investigations of the central part of the South Bačka loess terrace revealed the presence of 518 plant taxa, of which, 504 were at the species and 14 at the subspecies level (Table 1).

Taxonomic analysis

Recorded plant taxa were classified into 315 genera, 102 families, 76 orders, six classes, and four phyla. The phylum

Fig. 1. Position and map of the investigated localities (Anonymous, 1983a, 1983b; modified).

Equisetophyta was represented by three species (0.58%), whereas Polypodiophyta contained only one species (0.20%) – *Salvinia natans*. The phylum Pinophyta included 10 species with ornamental character (1.93%) arranged into four families and eight genera. With 504 taxa at the species and subspecies level, comprising 97.30% of the total number of taxa, the phylum Magnoliophyta absolutely dominated the entire sample. Within this phylum, 418 taxa at the species

and subspecies level were grouped into 252 genera: 78 families belonged to the class Magnoliopsida (80.69%), while the class Liliopsida was represented with 86 taxa (16.60%) grouped into 54 genera and 18 families.

Families with the largest number of taxa were Asteraceae (66), Poaceae (45), Rosaceae (35), Fabaceae (30), Lamiaceae (27), and Brassicaceae (23). Families Caryophyllaceae, Polygonaceae and Scrophulariaceae were represented with

14 taxa, and Apiaceae and Euphorbiaceae with 12 taxa, respectively. Boraginaceae, Cyperaceae, and Ranunculaceae had 11 taxa, while all other families were represented with less than 10 taxa. This taxonomic structure corresponds to the general family structure of the Serbian flora (Stevanović et al. 1995b). Although Asteraceae was the family with the largest number of representatives in the study area, it should be noted that a significant number of plant species from this family collected during field research belong to the group of non-native invasive species. However, even if we do not take into account these 16 invasive taxa in our analysis, Asteraceae family would still be the most diverse. The second most abundant family was Poaceae, which is as expected, considering that the investigated area is located in a steppe zone, and is under strong Pontic and Eurasian floristic influence. The Submediterranean floristic influence is emphasized by the presence of Fabaceae, Lamiaceae, and Caryophyllaceae, while a large number of species belonging to families Brassicaceae, Apiaceae, Cyperaceae, and Ranunculaceae indicate a strong Central European and Eurasian floristic impact (Stevanović et al. 1995b). Family Rosaceae was highly ranked among others, because a significant number of ornamental and cultivated plants, which were also collected during fieldwork, belong to this family.

The largest genus was *Euphorbia* (11 species), followed by *Prunus* (8 species) and other genera, which included seven (*Potentilla*, *Ranunculus* and *Rumex*) and five species (*Acer*, *Bromus*, *Carex*, *Epilobium*, and *Veronica*). This spec-

Fig. 2. Areal types spectrum of the flora of the central part of the South Bačka loess terrace. Legend: Adv - Adventitious, CEv - Central European, Cos - Cosmopolitan, EAs - Eurasian, Hol - Holarctic, MSm - Mediterranean-Submediterranean, PSs - Pontic-South Siberian, SAt - Subatlantic.

trum of genera was significantly different from that given for the flora of Serbia (Stevanović et al. 1995b). However, these differences in spectra, especially the great number of species in the *Euphorbia* and *Rumex* genera recorded in the present study, can be explained by the fact that they flourish in places under significant and constant anthropogenic influence, which were the most common habitats in our research area. Many cultivated and ornamental plants from the genera *Prunus* and *Acer* were also collected during the present investigation. In addition, some species from these genera have the ability to spontaneously expand into natural habitats, and this, coupled with the above mentioned, are the main reasons why the representatives of these two genera were found in such numbers. *Carex*, *Ranunculus*, *Potentilla*, and *Veronica* are among the most species-rich genera in the flora of Serbia (Stevanović et al. 1995b), so their high number in the present research area is not surprising.

Phytogeographical analysis

Floral elements of analyzed plant taxa were grouped into eight areal types (Fig. 2). Results have shown that the largest number of taxa – 150 (34.17%) belong to the Eurasian areal type. The recorded percentage was higher than that noted by Gajić (1984) for this part of Serbia (24.32%), implying a strong Eurasian floristic influence on the flora of the research area. As a consequence of a wide ecological valence, species from this areal type are usually distributed across the broad area of the Eurasian continent. Considering that the South Bačka loess terrace is under intensive anthropogenic pressure and that many natural habitats have been severely degraded in the process of creating arable land, species with a wider ecological valence, like the above mentioned Eurasian species, certainly have a better chance of prevailing in these unfavorable conditions. In addition, Holarctic (6.19%) and cosmopolitan (7.11%) species were also noted and together with Eurasian species make up a total of 47.47% of all vascular plant species in the investigated area.

Given that the investigated area is located in a steppe zone, a significant number of taxa from the Pontic-South Siberian areal type were expected. A total of 72 taxa (16.51%) were noted, most of them belonging to the Subpontic-Submediterranean and Subpontic-Central Asian floral elements. This number would certainly have been higher if not for the centuries of constant negative anthropogenic pressure on these steppe habitats. The Mediterranean-Submediterranean areal type is represented only by Submediterranean floral elements, which comprised 29 species (6.65%). These species often occupy the same habitats as those from the Subpontic-Submediterranean floral element, and together support the xerophytic character of the study area (Gajić 1984). Also, 68 species belonging to the Central European areal type were

recorded (15.60%). Only two species were not classified as a sub-Central European floral element, which indicates that the Central European flora in this region is represented with less characteristic species for this areal type (Gajić 1984). Six recorded species (1.38%) were members of the Subatlantic areal type.

If we compare the results of our phytogeographical analysis with the results recorded for a geographically close region – Bačka loess plateau (Igić 1991), we notice that most areal types were almost equally represented in both of the investigated areas. The biggest differences were observed in the representation of adventitious species, as well as those belonging to the Mediterranean-Submediterranean areal type. The dominant type of vegetation in the Bačka loess plateau are different associations with meadow-steppe character (Parabućski 1982) which are the dominant type of habitats for the species of the Mediterranean-Submediterranean areal type that can be found in this region (Gajić 1984). The absence of these types of habitats, or more precisely, their reduction to fragments of just several square meters in our investigated area, is the main reason for the large discrepancy between the share of Mediterranean-Submediterranean species in the Bačka loess plateau areal type spectrum – 16.48% (Igić 1991) and the one found in our study – 6.65%.

Comparing to the flora of the Bačka loess plateau, where 13 relicts was registred (Igić 1991), half as many relict species were noted in our research. Only six tertiary relicts, most of them primarily related to wet or aquatic habitats (*Butomus umbellatus*, *Hedera helix*, *Humulus lupulus*, *Hydrocharis morsus-ranae*, *Stratiotes aloides*, and *Trapa natans*), were observed in our investigation. The reason for such a large difference in the number of recorded relict species could be explained by the fact that all relicts registered in the study area are species with a wide geographical distribution. In contrast, relict species noted on the Bačka loess plateau have a Pontic-Pannonian, Pontic-Mediterranean, or Submediterranean distribution (Igić 1991), and in the area of Vojvodina inhabit only preserved steppe fragments, wet meadows or salt marshes, all habitats which were sparse in our investigated region.

It is also necessary to mention the adventive areal type, to which the non-native plants belong. In fact, this group represented a significant part of the areal type spectrum with 54 taxa (12.39%), of which 41 taxa had an invasive character (Lazarević et al. 2012; Anačkov et al. 2013). Also, nine more taxa that do not belong to the adventive areal type defined by Gajić (1984), could still be treated as invasive according to Anačkov et al. (2013). If we sum all of these species, we obtain a total of 50 taxa with an invasive character in the investigated area. There are many reasons that could explain

such a high presence of invasive taxa. First and foremost is the strong human influence on the remaining fragments of natural and semi-natural habitats. Consequently, this human influence lead to the formation of potentially new favourable sites for the introduction of invasive plant species. Also, the fringe areas of arable fields are inhabited by a significant number of invasive plants and have been recognized as important centers for the colonization and dispersion of invasive plants (Anačkov et al. 2013), probably because these areas lack agro-technical measures (mechanical or chemical suppression of weeds). Secondly, the presence of a well-developed road and railway network, as well as the DTD hydrosystem and Jegrička river, also facilitate the spread of invasive species (Rat et al. 2017). In the end, poor awareness of the local community about the problem that invasive species pose, and the lack of a clear strategy for their suppression is one more reason for the rapid spread of alien species within the study area.

Fig. 3. Biological spectrum of the flora of the central part of the South Bačka loess terrace. Legend: Ch - Chamaephytes, G - Geophytes, H - Hemicryptophytes, P - Phanerophytes, S - Scandentophytes, Par/Semipar - Saprophytes/Semiparasitophytes, T - Therophytes.

As mentioned above, the share of adventitious species in the areal type spectrum recorded in our present research (12.39%) is much larger then that recorded by Igić (1991) for the flora of the Bačka loess plateau (4.15%). Except for the already mentioned reasons for the high presence of these taxa in our investigated area, one more reason for the significant difference in the share of adventive areal type could be found in the fact that a significant period of time (25 years) has

past since these two investigations were carried out. In this period the Bačka loesse plateau has also been under negative human-influence, which probably had effected the floristic composition of the plateau. Bearing this in mind, it is possible that today the difference in the share of the adventive areal type between the central part of the South Bačka loess terrace and the Bačka loess plateau is less pronounced than our current data indicate.

Biological spectrum

The biological spectrum of the flora is characterized by eight life forms (Fig. 3). Hemicryptophytes were represented by 172 taxa (33.20%), while 145 taxa (27.99%) were therophytes. Based on this, we can conclude that the flora has a hemicrypto-therophytic character. Although the biological spectrum of the investigated area and the flora of Serbia have the same bipolar hemicrypto-therophytic character (Diklić 1984), there is a difference in the contribution of particular life forms. Comparing to the flora of Serbia, a smaller share of hemicryptophytes (46.8% – flora of Serbia) and a larger share of therophytes (18.5% – flora of Serbia) in the biological spectrum of the study area was noted. Therophytes are defined as annual plants that are, among other habitats, often found growing alongside roads, on waste grounds, pastures or any ruderal habitats that possess favorable conditions for their development (Diklić 1984). The listed habitat types, which were often present in the study area, are quite unstable (ephemeral) and therefore not suitable for the development of most perennial plants (hemicryptophytes). Also, many noted therophyte species are weeds that typically occur in agricultural areas. As most of the recorded adventive plants were part of this group, a higher presence of therophytes in the biological spectrum was expected. Phanerophytes with 99 taxa or a 19.11% share occupied third place on the general biological spectrum. The indicated number was significantly higher than the one (7.4%) stated for the flora of Serbia (Diklić 1984). This difference could be explained by the high number of ornamental and cultivated species of trees and shrubs present in the research area. If we were to exclude these plants from our analyses, we would obtain a total of 24 taxa or just 5.42% of phanerophytes in the life form spectrum. Geophytes were represented with 7.72%, and were mostly noted on preserved steppe fragments, or more often on wetlands. Considering that our research also included aquatic habitats, 25 hydrophytes were registered (4.83%), which is 20% of the total diversity of aquatic plants in Serbia (Diklić 1984). Scandentophytes (3.86%) and chamaephytes (2.51%) together with parasitic and semiparasitic (0.77%) plants were also recorded, but in minor percentages.

Threatened status

Twenty protected plant species from the list of “Rules on the protection of strictly protected and protected wild species of plants, animals and fungi” in the Republic of Serbia (Anonymous 2010a) were registered, mainly in preserved parts of natural habitats. Of this number, 16 are protected under control of use and trade in the territory of Serbia (Anonymous 2010b).

CONCLUSIONS

To date, the area of the South Bačka loess terrace has not been the subject of detailed botanical research, and only individual floristic records from this territory have been reported. The main reason for this may be the fact that this is an almost exclusively agricultural area without large zones of natural vegetation, and is thus an “uninteresting” area for botanists. Considering the fact that there is a gap in the knowledge of the floristic diversity of this region, field research was conducted in the central part of the terrace over a period of three years. A total of 518 plant taxa were registered and, of this number, 504 taxa were at the species and 14 at the subspecies level. The most species abundant families were Asteraceae, Poaceae, Rosaceae, Fabaceae, Lamiaceae, and Brassicaceae, which on one hand implies a strong Pontic floristic influence and on the other hand a strong Central European and Eurasian floristic influence on the flora of the study area. These influences were confirmed by phytogeographical analysis, which support the dominance of taxa belonging to Eurasian, Central European, and Pontic-South Siberian areal types. Also, the presence of a significant number of adventive plants (12.39%) indicated a strong negative human impact on natural habitats. The predominant plant life forms were hemicryptophytes and therophytes with a notable contribution of phanerophytes in the biological spectrum. Despite the strong anthropogenic influence and extremely devastated habitats, the central part of the South Bačka loess terrace is still characterized by a relatively large number of plant species, which encourage further investigations of these neglected and floristically “less interesting” areas.

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Table 1. Vascular flora of the central part of the South Bačka loess terrace.

Taxa	Life form	Areal type
Equisetopsida C. Agardh 1825		
Equisetaceae A. Michaux ex Alph. de Candolle 1804		
<i>Equisetum arvense</i> L. 1753	a Mes-Meg G rhiz	Hol
<i>Equisetum ramosissimum</i> Desf. 1799	a Mac-Alt Ch herb scap	Cos
<i>Equisetum telmateia</i> Ehrh. 1783	a Meg-Alt G rhiz	Hol
Polypodiopsida Cronquist, Takht. & Zimmerm. 1966		
Salviniaceae Lestiboudois 1826		
<i>Salvinia natans</i> (L.) All. 1785	er nat HydT	Hol
Ginkgoopsida Engl. 1898		
Ginkgoaceae Engl. 1897		
<i>Ginkgo biloba</i> L. 1771	fo dec Mes P scap	Orn
Pinopsida Burnett 1835		
Pinaceae Spreng. ex F. Rudolphi 1830		
<i>Larix decidua</i> Mill. 1768	ac dec Mes P scap	Orn
<i>Pinus nigra</i> J.F.Arnold 1785	ac semp Mes P scap	Orn
<i>Pinus sylvestris</i> L. 1753	ac semp Mes P scap	Orn
Cupressaceae Gray 1822		
<i>Chamaecyparis lawsoniana</i> (A.Murray bis) Parl. 1864	ac semp Mes P scap	Orn
<i>Juniperus horizontalis</i> Moench 1794	ac semp N P caesp	Orn
<i>Juniperus virginiana</i> L. 1753	ac semp Mes P scap	Orn
<i>Platycladus orientalis</i> (L.) Franco 1949	ac semp Mes P scap	Orn
<i>Thuja occidentalis</i> L. 1753	ac semp Mes P scap	Orn
Taxaceae Gray 1822		
<i>Taxus baccata</i> L. 1753	ac semp Mi P caesp/Mes P scap	Orn
Magnoliopsida Brongn. 1843		
Ceratophyllaceae Gray 1822		
<i>Ceratophyllum demersum</i> L. 1753	rad sbm HydG	Cos
<i>Ceratophyllum submersum</i> L. 1763	rad sbm HydG	CEv
Platanaceae T. Lestib. 1826		
<i>Platanus acerifolia</i> (Aiton) Willd. 1797	fo dec Mes P scap	Orn
<i>Platanus occidentalis</i> L. 1753	fo dec Mes P scap	Orn
Berberidaceae Juss. 1789		
<i>Berberis aquifolium</i> Pursh 1813	fo semp N P caesp	Orn
Ranunculaceae Juss. 1789		
<i>Clematis vitalba</i> L. 1753	a Alt S lig	SAt
<i>Consolida orientalis</i> (J.Gay) Schrödinger 1909	v-a Meg-Alt T scap	PSs
<i>Consolida regalis</i> Gray 1821	a Mes-Meg T scap	CEv
<i>Nigella arvensis</i> L. 1753	a Mes T scap	PSs
<i>Ranunculus acris</i> L. 1753	a Meg H scap semiros	EAs

Taxa	Life form	Areal type
<i>Ranunculus bulbosus</i> L. 1753	a Mes-Meg H scap	CEv
<i>Ranunculus polyanthemos</i> L. 1753	a Meg H scap semiros	PSs
<i>Ranunculus repens</i> L. 1753	a Mes-Meg H rept	EAs
<i>Ranunculus sardous</i> Crantz 1763	v Mes T caesp	CEv
<i>Ranunculus sceleratus</i> L. 1753	v-a Mes-Mac T scap/H scap	Hol
<i>Ranunculus trichophyllus</i> Chaix ex Vill. 1786	rad subm HydT	Hol
Papaveraceae Juss. 1789		
<i>Chelidonium majus</i> L. 1753	v-a Mes-Meg H semiros	EAs
<i>Papaver rhoeas</i> L. 1753	a Meg T scap	EAs
Fumariaceae Marquis 1820		
<i>Fumaria officinalis</i> L. 1753	v-a Mes T scap	EAs
Paeoniaceae Raf. 1815		
<i>Paeonia peregrina</i> Mill. 1768	a Alt G tub	Orn
Buxaceae Dumort. 1822		
<i>Buxus sempervirens</i> L. 1753	fo semp N P caesp	Orn
Fagaceae Dumort. 1829		
<i>Quercus robur</i> L. 1753	fo dec Mes P scap	Orn
Betulaceae Gray 1822		
<i>Betula pendula</i> Roth 1788	fo dec Mes P scap	Orn
Corylaceae Mirbel 1815		
<i>Corylus avellana</i> L. 1753	fo dec Mi P caesp/Mi P scap	Orn
<i>Corylus colurna</i> L. 1753	fo dec Mes P scap	Orn
<i>Corylus maxima</i> Mill. 1768	fo dec Mi P caesp/Mi P scap	Orn
Juglandaceae DC. ex Perleb 1818		
<i>Juglans nigra</i> L. 1753	fo dec Mes P scap	Orn
<i>Juglans regia</i> L. 1753	fo dec Mes P scap	Orn
Phytolaccaceae R. Br. 1818		
<i>Phytolacca americana</i> L. 1753	a Alt H scap	Adv
Portulacaceae Juss. 1789		
<i>Portulaca grandiflora</i> Hook. 1829	a Mes H succ	Orn
<i>Portulaca oleracea</i> L. 1753	a Mes T succ	Cos
Caryophyllaceae Juss. 1789		
<i>Cerastium dubium</i> (Bastard) Guépin 1838	v-a Mes T scap	PSs
<i>Cerastium fontanum</i> Baumg. 1816 subsp. <i>vulgare</i> (Hartm.) Greuter & Burdet 1982	v-a Mes fo dec Ch herb scap rept	Cos
<i>Dianthus barbatus</i> L. 1753	v-a Mac H scap	Msm
<i>Holosteum umbellatum</i> L. 1753	v Mes T ros	EAs
<i>Petrorhagia prolifera</i> (L.) P.W.Ball & Heywood 1964	v-a Mac T scap	PSs
<i>Sagina procumbens</i> L. 1753	v-a Mi fo dec Ch herb scap rept	Hol
<i>Saponaria officinalis</i> L. 1753	a Meg H scap	EAs
<i>Silene baccifera</i> (L.) Roth 1788	a Mi-Mes T scap	EAs
<i>Silene latifolia</i> Poir. 1789	v-a Mes-Meg T scap/H scap bienn	EAs
<i>Silene vulgaris</i> (Moench) Garcke 1869	a Mes H scap/G rad	EAs
<i>Stellaria aquatica</i> (L.) Scop. 1771	a Mi-Meg H scap rept/T scap rept	EAs
<i>Stellaria graminea</i> L. 1753	a Mes-Meg H scap	EAs
<i>Stellaria holostea</i> L. 1753	v-a Mes fo dec Ch herb scap rept	EAs
<i>Stellaria media</i> (L.) Vill. 1789	v-aut Mi T rept	Cos
Amaranthaceae Juss. 1789		
<i>Amaranthus blitoides</i> S.Watson 1877	a Mes T rept	Adv
<i>Amaranthus crispus</i> (Lesp. & Thévenau) A.Terracc. 1890	a-aut Mes T rept	Adv
<i>Amaranthus deflexus</i> L. 1771	a Mes-Mac G rhiz	Adv

Taxa	Life form	Areal type
<i>Amaranthus retroflexus</i> L. 1753	a Mes-Alt T scap	Adv
Chenopodiaceae Ventenat 1799		
<i>Atriplex prostrata</i> Boucher ex DC. 1805	a-aut Mes-Meg T scap rept	Hol
<i>Bassia scoparia</i> (L.) A.J.Scott 1978	a-aut Alt T scap	Adv
<i>Chenopodium album</i> L. 1753	a Meg-Alt T scap	Cos
<i>Chenopodium hybridum</i> L. 1753	v-aut Meg T scap	Hol
<i>Chenopodium vulvaria</i> L. 1753	a Mac T rept	CEv
Polygonaceae Juss. 1789		
<i>Fallopia convolvulus</i> (L.) Á.Löve 1970	a-aut Meg-Alt ST herb	EAs
<i>Fallopia dumetorum</i> (L.) Holub 1971	a-aut Meg-Alt ST herb	EAs
<i>Persicaria lapathifolia</i> (L.) Delarbre 1800	a-aut Meg T scap	Hol
<i>Persicaria maculosa</i> Gray 1821	a-aut Mac-Meg T caesp/scap	EAs
<i>Persicaria orientalis</i> (L.) Spach 1841	a Meg-Alt T scap	Adv
<i>Polygonum aviculare</i> L. 1753	v-aut Mes-Mac T caesp/scap	Cos
<i>Reynoutria japonica</i> Houtt. 1777	a Alt G rhiz	Adv
<i>Rumex conglomeratus</i> Murray 1770	a Mac-Meg H scap	EAs
<i>Rumex crispus</i> L. 1753	a Meg H scap	EAs
<i>Rumex hydrolapathum</i> Huds. 1778	a Meg-Alt H scap	CEv
<i>Rumex obtusifolius</i> L. 1753	a Meg H scap	CEv
<i>Rumex palustris</i> Sm. 1800	a Mac T scap/H scap bienn	CEv
<i>Rumex pulcher</i> L. 1753	v-a Mes-Mac H ros	MSm
<i>Rumex stenophyllus</i> Ledeb. 1830	a Meg H scap	PSs
Tamaricaceae Link 1821		
<i>Tamarix parviflora</i> DC. 1828	fo dec Mi P caesp	Orn
Hypericaceae Juss. 1789		
<i>Hypericum perforatum</i> L. 1753	a Mes-Meg H scap	EAs
Primulaceae Batsch ex Borkh. 1797		
<i>Anagallis arvensis</i> L. 1753	v-aut Mi T rept scap	Cos
<i>Anagallis arvensis</i> L. 1753 subsp. <i>foemina</i> (Mill.) Schinz & Thell. 1907	v Mi T rept scap	Cos
<i>Lysimachia nummularia</i> L. 1753	v N-Mi fo dec Ch herb rept	CEv
<i>Lysimachia vulgaris</i> L. 1753	a Mac-Meg H scap	EAs
Salicaceae Mirb. 1815		
<i>Populus alba</i> L. 1753	fo dec Mes P scap	EAs
<i>Populus deltoides</i> Marshall 1785	fo dec Mes P scap	Orn
<i>Populus nigra</i> L. 1753	fo dec Mes P scap	Orn
<i>Populus tremula</i> L. 1753	fo dec Mes P scap	Orn
<i>Salix alba</i> L. 1753	fo dec Mes P scap	EAs
<i>Salix babylonica</i> L. 1753	fo dec Mes P scap	EAs
<i>Salix cinerea</i> L. 1753	fo dec Mi P caesp	EAs
<i>Salix triandra</i> L. 1753	fo dec Mi P caesp/Mes P scap	EAs
Violaceae Batsch 1802		
<i>Viola arvensis</i> Murray 1770	v-aut Mi-Mac T scap	EAs
<i>Viola kitaibeliana</i> Schult. 1819	v-a Mi-Mes T scap	PSs
<i>Viola odorata</i> L. 1753	v Mi-Mes H rept ros	SAt
Cucurbitaceae Juss. 1789		
<i>Bryonia alba</i> L. 1753	a Alt SH herb	PSs
<i>Echinocystis lobata</i> (Michx.) Torr. & A.Gray 1840	a Alt ST herb	Adv
Brassicaceae Burnett 1835		
<i>Alliaria petiolata</i> (M.Bieb.) Cavara & Grande 1913	v-a Meg H scap bienn	CEv
<i>Arabidopsis thaliana</i> (L.) Heynh. 1842	v Mes-Mac T ros/H ros bienn	EAs
<i>Armoracia rusticana</i> P. Gaertn., B. Mey. & Scherb. 1800	v-a Mes-Meg G rhiz	Adv

Taxa	Life form	Areal type
<i>Brassica napus</i> L. 1753	v Mac-Alt T scap/H scap bienn	Adv
<i>Calepina irregularis</i> (Asso) Thell. 1905	a Mes-Meg T scap	MSm
<i>Camelina microcarpa</i> Andrz. ex DC. 1821	v-a Mes-Mac T scap	EAs
<i>Capsella bursa-pastoris</i> (L.) Medik. 1792	v-aut Mi-Meg T ros/H ros bienn	Cos
<i>Descurainia sophia</i> (L.) Webb ex Prantl 1892	v-a Mes-Meg T scap	EAs
<i>Diplotaxis muralis</i> (L.) DC. 1821	v-a Mes-Mac T ros/H ros bienn	MSm
<i>Erophila verna</i> (L.) DC. 1821	v N-Mi T ros	Hol
<i>Lepidium campestre</i> (L.) R.Br. 1812	a Meg T scap/H scap bienn	CEv
<i>Lepidium draba</i> L. 1753	v-a Mes-Mac H scap	PSs
<i>Lepidium perfoliatum</i> L. 1753	v Mes-Mac T scap/H scap bienn	PSs
<i>Myagrum perfoliatum</i> L. 1753	v Mes-Mac T scap	MSm
<i>Rorippa × anceps</i> (Wahlenb.) Rchb. 1838	v-a Mac-Meg H scap/G rhiz	
<i>Rorippa austriaca</i> (Crantz) Spach 1838	v-a Mac-Meg H scap/G rhiz	PSs
<i>Rorippa kernerii</i> Menyh. 1877	v-a Mi-Mac H ros bienn	PSs
<i>Sinapis arvensis</i> L. 1753	v-a Mes-Meg T scap	EAs
<i>Sisymbrium altissimum</i> L. 1753	v-a Mes-Mac T scap/H scap bienn	PSs
<i>Sisymbrium loeselii</i> L. 1755	v-a Mes-Mac T scap/H scap bienn	PSs
<i>Sisymbrium officinale</i> (L.) Scop. 1772	a Meg T scap	EAs
<i>Thlaspi arvense</i> L. 1753	v-a Mes T scap	EAs
<i>Thlaspi perfoliatum</i> L. 1753	v-a Mes T ros	CEv
Resedaceae Martinov 1820		
<i>Reseda lutea</i> L. 1753	v-a Mac T scap/H scap	CEv
Tiliaceae A.L. de Jussieu 1789		
<i>Tilia cordata</i> Mill. 1768	fo dec Mes P scap	Orn
<i>Tilia platyphyllos</i> Scop. 1771	fo dec Mes P scap	Orn
<i>Tilia tomentosa</i> Moench 1785	fo dec Mes P scap	Orn
Malvaceae Juss. 1789		
<i>Abutilon theophrasti</i> Medic. 1787	a Mac-Alt T scap	Adv
<i>Alcea rosea</i> L. 1753	v-a Alt H scap	Adv
<i>Althaea officinalis</i> L. 1753	a-aut Mac-Alt H scap	PSs
<i>Hibiscus syriacus</i> L. 1753	fo dec Mi P caesp	Orn
<i>Hibiscus trionum</i> L. 1753	a Mes-Mac T scap	PSs
<i>Malva neglecta</i> Wallr. 1824	a Mes-Mac T scap/H scap	EAs
<i>Malva sylvestris</i> L. 1753	a Meg-Alt H scap bienn	EAs
Ulmaceae Mirb. 1815		
<i>Celtis occidentalis</i> L. 1753	fo dec Mes P scap	Orn
<i>Ulmus glabra</i> Huds. 1762	fo dec Mes P scap	CEv
<i>Ulmus parvifolia</i> Jacq. 1798	fo dec Mes P scap	Orn
<i>Ulmus pumila</i> L. 1753	fo dec Mes P scap	Orn
<i>Zelkova carpinifolia</i> (Pall.) K. Koch 1849	fo dec Mes P scap	Orn
Moraceae Gaudich. 1835		
<i>Broussonetia papyrifera</i> (L.) L'Hér. ex Vent. 1799	fo dec Mes P scap	Orn
<i>Maclura pomifera</i> (Raf.) C.K.Schneid. 1906	fo dec Mes P scap	Orn
<i>Morus alba</i> L. 1753	fo dec Mes P scap	Adv
<i>Morus nigra</i> L. 1753	fo dec Mes P scap	Adv
Cannabaceae Martinov 1820		
<i>Humulus lupulus</i> L. 1753	a Alt SH herb	EAs
Urticaceae Juss. 1789		
<i>Urtica dioica</i> L. 1753	a Meg-Alt H scap	EAs
<i>Urtica urens</i> L. 1753	a Mes-Mac T scap	EAs
Euphorbiaceae Juss. 1789		

Taxa	Life form	Areal type
<i>Euphorbia cyparissias</i> L. 1753	a Mes-Meg H scap	EAs
<i>Euphorbia esula</i> L. 1753	a Mac-Meg H scap	EAs
<i>Euphorbia esula</i> L. 1753 subsp. <i>tommasiniana</i> (Bertol.) Kuzmanov 1979	a Mac-Meg H scap	PSs
<i>Euphorbia falcata</i> L. 1753	a Mes T scap	PSs
<i>Euphorbia helioscopia</i> L. 1753	v-aut Mes T scap	EAs
<i>Euphorbia illirica</i> Lam. 1788	v-a Mac-Alt G rhiz	EAs
<i>Euphorbia lathyris</i> L. 1753	a Mes-Meg T scap/H scap bienn	Adv
<i>Euphorbia maculata</i> L. 1753	a Mi T rept	Adv
<i>Euphorbia pannonica</i> Host 1831	v-a Mes-Mac H scap	PSs
<i>Euphorbia peplus</i> L. 1753	a Mes T scap	EAs
<i>Euphorbia platyphyllos</i> L. 1753	a-aut Mes-Meg T scap	Msm
<i>Ricinus communis</i> L. 1753	a-aut Alt T scap	Adv
Crassulaceae J. St.-Hil. 1805		
<i>Sedum album</i> L. 1753	a Mi-Mes Ch herb scap succ	CEv
Haloragaceae R. Br. 1814		
<i>Myriophyllum spicatum</i> L. 1753	rhiz sbm HydG	Hol
<i>Myriophyllum verticillatum</i> L. 1753	rhiz sbm HydG	Hol
Saxifragaceae Juss. 1789		
<i>Saxifraga tridactylites</i> L. 1753	a-aut Mes T scap	CEv
Vitaceae Juss. 1789		
<i>Parthenocissus quinquefolia</i> (L.) Planch. 1887	a Alt S lig	Adv
<i>Vitis vulpina</i> L. 1753	a Alt S lig	Adv
Rosaceae Juss. 1789		
<i>Agrimonia eupatoria</i> L. 1753	a Meg H scap	EAs
<i>Chaenomeles japonica</i> (Thunb.) Lindl. ex Spach 1834	fo dec/sem P caesp	Orn
<i>Cotoneaster horizontalis</i> Decne. 1877	fo dec/sem P caesp	Orn
<i>Cotoneaster integerrimus</i> Medik. 1793	fo dec N P caesp	Orn
<i>Crataegus monogyna</i> Jacq. 1775	fo dec N-Mi P caesp/Mi P scap	CEv
<i>Cydonia oblonga</i> Mill. 1768	fo dec Mi P caesp/Mi-Mes P scap	Orn
<i>Fragaria viridis</i> Weston 1771	v Mes H ros/G rhiz	EAs
<i>Geum urbanum</i> L. 1753	a Meg H scap	EAs
<i>Kerria japonica</i> (L.) DC. 1818	fo dec N-Mi P caesp	Orn
<i>Malus domestica</i> Borkh. 1803	fo dec Mes P scap	Orn
<i>Potentilla anserina</i> L. 1753	v-a Mes-Meg H rept	Hol
<i>Potentilla argentea</i> L. 1753	a Mes-Meg H scap	PSs
<i>Potentilla fruticosa</i> L. 1753	v-a Mes fo dec Ch suffr caesp	Orn
<i>Potentilla incana</i> P. Gaertn., B.Mey. & Scherb. 1800	v Mi-Mes fo dec Ch herb caesp	PSs
<i>Potentilla recta</i> L. 1753	a Mes-Meg H scap	PSs
<i>Potentilla reptans</i> L. 1753	a Mi-Mes H rept	EAs
<i>Potentilla supina</i> L. 1753	a-aut Mes-Mac T rept/H rept	EAs
<i>Prunus armeniaca</i> L. 1753	fo dec Mi P caesp/Mi-Mes P scap	Orn
<i>Prunus avium</i> (L.) L. 1755	fo dec Mes P scap	Orn
<i>Prunus cerasifera</i> Ehrh. 1785	fo dec Mi P caesp/Mi-Mes P scap	EAs
<i>Prunus cerasus</i> L. 1753	fo dec Mi P caesp/Mi-Mes P scap	Orn
<i>Prunus domestica</i> L. 1753	fo dec Mi P caesp/Mi-Mes P scap	Orn
<i>Prunus laurocerasus</i> L. 1753	fo semp Mes P caesp/Mes P scap	Orn
<i>Prunus persica</i> (L.) Stokes 1812	fo dec Mi-Mes P scap	Orn
<i>Prunus spinosa</i> L. 1753	fo dec N P caesp	PSs
<i>Pyracantha coccinea</i> M.Roem. 1847	fo semp N-Mi P caesp	Orn
<i>Pyrus communis</i> L. 1753	fo dec Mes P scap	Orn
<i>Pyrus communis</i> L. 1753 subsp. <i>pyraster</i> (L.) Ehrh. 1780	fo dec Mes P scap	CEv

Taxa	Life form	Areal type
<i>Rosa canina</i> L. 1753	fo dec N P caesp	CEv
<i>Rubus armeniacus</i> Focke 1874	fo dec N/Mi P caesp	Adv
<i>Rubus caesius</i> L. 1753	fo dec N P caesp	EAs
<i>Rubus caesius</i> L. x <i>hirtus</i> W. et K.	fo dec N P caesp	
<i>Sanguisorba minor</i> Scop. 1771	a Mi-Mes H ros	EAs
<i>Sorbus intermedia</i> (Ehrh.) Pers. 1806	fo dec Mes P scap	Orn
<i>Spiraea media</i> Schmidt 1792	fo dec N P caesp	Orn
Lythraceae J. St.-Hil. 1805		
<i>Lythrum tribracteatum</i> Salzm. ex Spreng. 1827	v-a Mes T scap	PSs
<i>Lythrum virgatum</i> L. 1753	a Mac-Meg H scap/G rhiz	EAs
Trapaceae Dumortier 1829		
<i>Trapa natans</i> L. 1753	rad nat HydT	EAs
Onagraceae Juss. 1789		
<i>Epilobium angustifolium</i> L. 1753	a Mes-Alt H scap	Hol
<i>Epilobium hirsutum</i> L. 1753	a-aut Mac-Meg H scap/G rhiz	CEv
<i>Epilobium hirsutum</i> L. 1753 subsp. <i>lamyi</i> (F.W.Schultz) Nyman 1879	a Mac-Alt H scap/G rhiz	EAs
<i>Epilobium parviflorum</i> Schreb. 1771	a-aut Mes-Meg H scap	EAs
<i>Epilobium tetragonum</i> L. 1753	a-aut Mac-Meg H scap/G rhiz	EAs
<i>Oenothera biennis</i> L. 1753	a Meg-Alt H scap bienn	Adv
Fabaceae Lindl. 1836		
<i>Albizia julibrissin</i> Durazz. 1772	fo dec Mes P scap	Orn
<i>Amorpha fruticosa</i> L. 1753	fo dec Mi P caesp	Adv
<i>Astragalus cicer</i> L. 1753	a Mes-Mac H scap rept	PSs
<i>Astragalus glycyphyllos</i> L. 1753	a Mes-Meg H scap rept	PSs
<i>Astragalus onobrychis</i> L. 1753	a Mes-Mac H scap rept	PSs
<i>Cercis siliquastrum</i> L. 1753	fo dec Mes P caesp/P scap	Orn
<i>Gleditsia triacanthos</i> L. 1753	fo dec Mes P scap	Adv
<i>Lathyrus hirsutus</i> L. 1753	v-a Meg T scap	MSm
<i>Lathyrus pratensis</i> L. 1753	a Meg H scap	EAs
<i>Lathyrus tuberosus</i> L. 1753	a Meg G tub rept	EAs
<i>Lotus corniculatus</i> L. 1753	a Mes H scap	EAs
<i>Lotus glaber</i> Mill. 1768	a Mes H scap	CEv
<i>Medicago falcata</i> L. 1753	a Mes-Meg H scap	PSs
<i>Medicago lupulina</i> L. 1753	a Mes T scap/H scap	EAs
<i>Medicago minima</i> (L.) L. 1754	v Mac T scap rept	PSs
<i>Medicago sativa</i> L. 1753	a Mes-Meg H scap	Adv
<i>Melilotus albus</i> Medik. 1787	a Meg-Alt T scap/H scap bienn	CEv
<i>Melilotus officinalis</i> (L.) Pall. 1776	a Meg-Alt H scap bienn	EAs
<i>Ononis spinosa</i> L. 1753	a-aut Mes-Meg fo dec Ch suffr caesp	CEv
<i>Robinia pseudoacacia</i> L. 1753	fo dec Mes P scap	Adv
<i>Securigera varia</i> (L.) Lassen 1989	a Meg H scap	PSs
<i>Styphnolobium japonicum</i> (L.) Schott 1830	fo dec Mes P scap	Orn
<i>Trifolium angustifolium</i> L. 1753	a Mes T scap	MSm
<i>Trifolium campestre</i> Schreb. 1804	a Mes T scap	CEv
<i>Trifolium pratense</i> L. 1753	a Mes H scap	EAs
<i>Trifolium repens</i> L. 1753	a Mi H rept	EAs
<i>Vicia cracca</i> L. 1753	a Meg-Alt SH herb/H scap	EAs
<i>Vicia grandiflora</i> Scop. 1772	v Meg-Alt ST herb/T scap	PSs
<i>Vicia hirsuta</i> (L.) Gray 1821	a Mes-Meg ST herb/T scap	EAs
<i>Vicia sativa</i> L. 1753 subsp. <i>nigra</i> (L.) Ehrh. 1780	a Mes-Meg ST herb/T scap	CEv

Taxa	Life form	Areal type
Oxalidaceae R. Br. 1818		
<i>Oxalis corniculata</i> L. 1753	a Mes T/H rept/scap	Msm
Sapindaceae Juss. 1789		
<i>Koelreuteria paniculata</i> Laxm. 1772	fo dec Mes P scap	Orn
Hippocastanaceae A.P. de Candolle 1824		
<i>Aesculus hippocastanum</i> L. 1753	fo dec Mes P scap	Orn
Aceraceae Durande 1782		
<i>Acer campestre</i> L. 1753	fo dec Mes P scap	Orn
<i>Acer negundo</i> L. 1753	fo dec Mes P scap	Orn
<i>Acer platanoides</i> L. 1753	fo dec Mes P scap	Orn
<i>Acer pseudoplatanus</i> L. 1753	fo dec Mes P scap	Orn
<i>Acer saccharinum</i> L. 1753	fo dec Mes P scap	Orn
Rutaceae Juss. 1789		
<i>Phellodendron amurense</i> Rupr. 1857	fo dec Mes P scap	Orn
Simaroubaceae DC. 1811		
<i>Ailanthus altissima</i> (Mill.) Swingle 1916	fo dec Mes P scap	Adv
Anacardiaceae R. Br. 1818		
<i>Rhus typhina</i> L. 1756	fo dec Mi P caesp	Orn
Geraniaceae Juss. 1789		
<i>Erodium cicutarium</i> (L.) L'Hér. 1789	v-a Mes T scap/H scap bienn	EAs
<i>Geranium dissectum</i> L. 1755	v-a Mes-Mac T scap	EAs
Zygophyllaceae R. Br. 1814		
<i>Tribulus terrestris</i> L. 1753	aut Mes-Mac T rept	PSs
Linaceae DC. ex Perleb 1818		
<i>Linum austriacum</i> L. 1753	v-a Mac H scap	PSs
Celastraceae R. Br. 1814		
<i>Euonymus europaeus</i> L. 1753	fo dec Mi P caesp/Mes P scap	CEv
Santalaceae R. Br. 1810		
<i>Thesium dollineri</i> Murb. ex Velen. 1891	a Mes H caesp	Msm
Rhamnaceae Juss. 1789		
<i>Rhamnus cathartica</i> L. 1753	fo dec Mi P caesp/scap	Orn
Elaeagnaceae Juss. 1789		
<i>Elaeagnus angustifolia</i> L. 1753	fo dec Mes P scap	Orn
Hydrangeaceae Dumort. 1829		
<i>Philadelphus coronarius</i> L. 1753	fo dec N-Mi P caesp	Orn
Cornaceae Bercht. & J. Presl 1825		
<i>Cornus sanguinea</i> L. 1753	fo dec Mi P caesp	CEv
Viburnaceae Rafinesque 1820		
<i>Viburnum opulus</i> L. 1753	fo dec N-Mi P caesp	Orn
Sambucaceae Batsch ex Borckhausen 1797		
<i>Sambucus ebulus</i> L. 1753	a Alt G rad/H scap	PSs
<i>Sambucus nigra</i> L. 1753	fo dec Mi P caesp/Mi-Mes P scap	CEv
Valerianaceae Batsch 1802		
<i>Valeriana officinalis</i> L. 1753	a Meg-Alt H scap	EAs
<i>Valerianella dentata</i> (L.) Pollich 1776	v-a Mes-Mac T scap	PSs
<i>Valerianella locusta</i> (L.) Laterr. 1821	a Mes T scap	Msm
Dipsacaceae Juss. 1789		
<i>Dipsacus fullonum</i> L. 1753	a Meg-Alt H scap bienn	CEv
<i>Dipsacus laciniatus</i> L. 1753	a Meg-Alt H scap bienn	PSs
<i>Knautia arvensis</i> (L.) Coult. 1823	a Mes-Meg H scap bienn	CEv

Taxa	Life form	Areal type
<i>Scabiosa ochroleuca</i> L. 1753	a Meg H scap	PSs
Araliaceae Juss. 1789		
<i>Hedera helix</i> L. 1753	aut semp Alt S lig	SAt
Apiaceae Lindl. 1836		
<i>Anethum graveolens</i> L. 1753	a Mac-Meg T scap	Adv
<i>Anthriscus cerefolium</i> (L.) Hoffm. 1814	v-a Mac-Meg T scap	PSs
<i>Conium maculatum</i> L. 1753	v-a Mac-Alt T ros/H ros bienn	EAs
<i>Daucus carota</i> L. 1753	a Meg H scap/T scap	EAs
<i>Eryngium campestre</i> L. 1753	a Mes-Meg H scap	PSs
<i>Falcaria vulgaris</i> Bernh. 1800	a Mac-Meg T scap/H scap bienn	PSs
<i>Oenanthe aquatica</i> (L.) Poir. 1798	v-a Mes-Alt T scap/H scap bienn	CEv
<i>Orlaya grandiflora</i> (L.) Hoffm. 1814	v-a Mes-Mac T scap	Msm
<i>Pastinaca sativa</i> L. 1753	a Mac-Meg H scap	EAs
<i>Pimpinella saxifraga</i> L. 1753	a Mes-Mac H scap	EAs
<i>Seseli annuum</i> L. 1753	a Mes-Mac H scap bienn	PSs
<i>Torilis arvensis</i> (Huds.) Link 1821	a Mes T scap	EAs
Asteraceae Bercht. & J. Presl 1820		
<i>Achillea millefolium</i> L. 1753	a Meg H scap	EAs
<i>Ambrosia artemisiifolia</i> L. 1753	a-aut Mes-Alt T scap	Adv
<i>Ambrosia trifida</i> L. 1753	a-aut Mes-Alt T scap	Adv
<i>Arctium lappa</i> L. 1753	a Alt H scap bienn	EAs
<i>Artemisia annua</i> L. 1753	a-aut Mac-Alt T scap	EAs
<i>Artemisia campestris</i> L. 1753	a-aut Mac-Alt fo dec Ch herb scap/G rhiz	PSs
<i>Artemisia vulgaris</i> L. 1753	a-aut Meg-Alt H scap/G rhiz	Hol
<i>Bellis perennis</i> L. 1753	a Mes H ros	CEv
<i>Bidens frondosa</i> L. 1753	aut Mes-Alt T scap	Adv
<i>Bidens tripartita</i> L. 1753	aut Mes-Alt T scap	CEv
<i>Carduus acanthoides</i> L. 1753	a Meg-Alt H scap bienn	CEv
<i>Carduus nutans</i> L. 1753	v-a Mes-Meg H scap bienn/T scap	EAs
<i>Carlina biebersteinii</i> Bernh. ex Hornem. 1819 subsp. <i>brevibracteata</i> (Andrae) K.Werner 1994	a-aut Mes-Meg H scap bienn	EAs
<i>Centaurea jacea</i> L. 1753 subsp. <i>banatica</i> (Roch.) Hayek 1912	a Mac-Meg H scap	EAs
<i>Centaurea jacea</i> L. 1753	a Mac-Meg H scap	EAs
<i>Centaurea stoebe</i> Tausch 1829 subsp. <i>australis</i> (Pančić ex A.Kern.) Greuter 2003	a Mac-Meg H scap	PSs
<i>Cichorium intybus</i> L. 1753	a-aut Meg-Alt H scap	EAs
<i>Cirsium arvense</i> (L.) Scop. 1772	a Meg-Alt G rad	EAs
<i>Cirsium eriophorum</i> (L.) Scop. 1772	a Meg-Alt H scap bienn	CEv
<i>Cirsium vulgare</i> (Savi) Ten. 1835	a Meg-Alt H scap bienn	EAs
<i>Cota austriaca</i> (Jacq.) Sch.Bip. 1854	a Mes-Mac T scap/H scap bienn	PSs
<i>Crepis biennis</i> L. 1753	a Mes-Meg H scap bienn	CEv
<i>Crepis foetida</i> L. 1753 subsp. <i>rhoeadifolia</i> (M.Bieb.) Čelak. 1871	a Mes-Meg T scap/H scap bienn	PSs
<i>Crepis pulchra</i> L. 1753	v-a Mes-Meg T scap	Msm
<i>Crepis setosa</i> Haller 1797	v-a Mes-Meg T scap	Msm
<i>Cyanus segetum</i> Hill 1762	v-a Mes-Meg T scap	Msm
<i>Erigeron annuus</i> (L.) Pers. 1807	a Mes-Meg T scap/H scap bienn	Adv
<i>Erigeron canadensis</i> L. 1753	a Meg-Alt T scap	Adv
<i>Eupatorium cannabinum</i> L. 1753	a-aut Mac-Alt H scap	CEv
<i>Galinsoga parviflora</i> Cav. 1796	a Mes-Meg T scap	Adv
<i>Helianthus annuus</i> L. 1753	a-aut Mac-Alt T scap	Adv
<i>Helminthotheca echioides</i> (L.) Holub 1973	a Mes-Meg T scap	Msm

Taxa	Life form	Areal type
<i>Inula britannica</i> L. 1753	a Mes-Meg H scap	CEv
<i>Inula helenium</i> L. 1753	a Meg-Alt H scap/G rhiz	EAs
<i>Iva xanthifolia</i> Nutt. 1818	a Alt T scap	Adv
<i>Lactuca saligna</i> L. 1753	a Mac-Meg T scap/H scap bienn	PSs
<i>Lactuca serriola</i> L. 1756	a Meg-Alt H scap bienn/T scap	PSs
<i>Leontodon hispidus</i> L. 1753	a Mes-Meg H ros	CEv
<i>Leucanthemum ircutianum</i> (Turcz.) Turcz. ex DC. 1838	v-aut Mes-Meg H scap	EAs
<i>Matricaria chamomilla</i> L. 1753	v-aut Mes-Mac T scap	EAs
<i>Onopordum acanthium</i> L. 1753	v-a Mac-Alt H scap bienn	PSs
<i>Picris hieracioides</i> L. 1753	a-aut Meg-Alt H scap bienn	PSs
<i>Pilosella caespitosa</i> (Dumort.) P.D.Sell & C.West 1967	v-a Mes-Mac H scap/G rhiz	EAs
<i>Pilosella officinarum</i> Vaill. 1754	a Mi-Mac H ros	CEv
<i>Podospermum canum</i> C.A.Mey. 1831	v Mi-Mac H scap/G rhiz	Msm
<i>Pulicaria dysenterica</i> (L.) Bernh. 1800	a Mes-Meg H scap	SAt
<i>Rudbeckia hirta</i> L. 1753	a Mac-Alt H scap bienn	Adv
<i>Rudbeckia laciniata</i> L. 1753	a-aut Mac-Alt G rhiz	Adv
<i>Senecio erucifolius</i> L. 1753	a Mac-Meg H scap/G rhiz	EAs
<i>Senecio leucanthemifolius</i> Poir. 1789 subsp. <i>vernalis</i> (Waldst. & Kit.) Greuter 2003	v Mi-Mac T scap	PSs
<i>Senecio vulgaris</i> L. 1753	v-aut Mi-Mes T scap/H scap bienn	EAs
<i>Solidago gigantea</i> Aiton 1789	a-aut Mac-Alt H scap	Adv
<i>Sonchus arvensis</i> L. 1753	a Mac-Alt H scap/G rhiz	EAs
<i>Sonchus asper</i> (L.) Hill 1769	a-aut Mac-Meg T scap	EAs
<i>Sonchus oleraceus</i> (L.) L. 1753	a Mac-Meg T scap	EAs
<i>Symphytotrichum</i> × <i>versicolor</i> (Willd.) G.L.Nesom 1995	a-aut Mac-Alt H scap	Adv
<i>Symphytotrichum tradescantii</i> (L.) G.L.Nesom 1995	a-aut Mac-Alt H scap/G rhiz	Adv
<i>Taraxacum officinale</i> Weber 1780	v-aut Mes H ros	EAs
<i>Tanacetum vulgare</i> L. 1753	a-aut Mac-Alt H scap	EAs
<i>Tragopogon dubius</i> Scop. 1772	v-a Mes-Mac H scap bienn	PSs
<i>Tragopogon orientalis</i> L. 1753	v-a Mes-Mac H scap bienn	EAs
<i>Tripleurospermum inodorum</i> (L.) Sch.Bip. 1844	v-a Mes-Mac T scap/H scap bienn	EAs
<i>Tripolium pannonicum</i> (Jacq.) Dobrocz. 1962	v-a Mi-Mes H scap bienn	PSs
<i>Tussilago farfara</i> L. 1753	v Mi-Mes G rhiz	EAs
<i>Xanthium orientale</i> L. 1763 subsp. <i>italicum</i> (Moretti) Greuter 2003	a Meg-Alt T scap	Adv
<i>Xanthium spinosum</i> L. 1753	a Mes-Mac T scap	Adv
Rubiaceae Juss. 1789		
<i>Asperula cynanchica</i> L. 1753	a Mes-Mac H caesp/G rhiz	PSs
<i>Galium aparine</i> L. 1753	v-a Mes-Meg ST herb	EAs
<i>Galium constrictum</i> Chaub.	v-a Mes-Mac H scap	Msm
<i>Galium mollugo</i> L. 1753	v-aut Mes-Meg SH herb	CEv
<i>Galium verum</i> L. 1753	a Mes-Meg H scap	EAs
Gentianaceae Juss. 1789		
<i>Centaurium erythraea</i> Rafn 1800	a Mi-Mes H bienn/T scap	CEv
<i>Centaurium pulchellum</i> (Sw.) Druce 1898	a Mi-Mes T scap/H scap bienn	EAs
Apocynaceae Juss. 1789		
<i>Asclepias syriaca</i> L. 1762	a Meg-Alt G rhiz	Adv
<i>Vinca minor</i> L. 1753	v Mes fo semp Ch suffr rept	CEv
<i>Vincetoxicum hirundinaria</i> Medik. 1790	a Mes-Meg H scap	PSs
Solanaceae Juss. 1789		
<i>Datura stramonium</i> L. 1753	a-aut Meg-Alt T scap	Cos
<i>Hyoscyamus niger</i> L. 1753	a Mes-Meg H scap bienn/T scap	EAs
<i>Lycium barbarum</i> L. 1753	fo dec N-Mi P caesp	Adv

Taxa	Life form	Areal type
<i>Solanum americanum</i> Mill. 1768	v-aut Mes-Meg T scap	Cos
<i>Solanum dulcamara</i> L. 1753	a Meg-Alt S lig	EAs
Convolvulaceae Juss. 1789		
<i>Calystegia sepium</i> (L.) R. Br. 1810	a Alt rhiz SG herb	EAs
<i>Convolvulus arvensis</i> L. 1753	a Alt rhiz SG herb	Cos
Cuscutaceae (Dumortier) Dumortier 1829		
<i>Cuscuta campestris</i> Yunck. 1932	v-aut Mes-Alt scand Par T	Adv
<i>Cuscuta epithymum</i> (L.) L. 1774	v-aut Mes-Alt scand Par T	EAs
Boraginaceae Juss. 1789		
<i>Anchusa officinalis</i> L. 1753	a Meg H scap bienn	CEv
<i>Asperugo procumbens</i> L. 1753	v Mac-Meg T scap	EAs
<i>Buglossoides arvensis</i> (L.) I.M.Johnst. 1954	v-a Mes T scap/H scap bienn	EAs
<i>Cerinth minor</i> L. 1753	v Mac H scap bienn	PSs
<i>Cynoglossum officinale</i> L. 1753	v Mac H ros bienn	EAs
<i>Echium vulgare</i> L. 1753	a Mes-Meg H scap	CEv
<i>Heliotropium europaeum</i> L. 1753	a Mes H scap	PSs
<i>Myosotis arvensis</i> (L.) Hill 1764	a Mes H scap bienn	EAs
<i>Myosotis discolor</i> Pers. 1798	v-a Mi-Mes T scap	CEv
<i>Nonea pulla</i> (L.) DC. 1805	v-a Mes-Mac H scap bienn	PSs
<i>Symphytum officinale</i> L. 1753	a Mes-Meg H scap	CEv
Oleaceae Hoffmanns. & Link 1809		
<i>Forsythia europaea</i> Degen & Bald. 1898	fo dec Mi P caesp	Orn
<i>Fraxinus angustifolia</i> Vahl 1804 subsp. <i>oxycarpa</i> (Willd.) Franco & Rocha Afonso	fo dec Mes P scap	Orn
<i>Fraxinus excelsior</i> L. 1753	fo dec Mes P scap	Orn
<i>Fraxinus pennsylvanica</i> Marshall 1785	fo dec Mes P scap	Orn
<i>Ligustrum vulgare</i> L. 1753	fo dec Mi P caesp	Orn
<i>Syringa vulgaris</i> L. 1753	fo dec Mi P caesp	Orn
Scrophulariaceae Juss. 1789		
<i>Chaenorhinum minus</i> (L.) Lange 1870	a-aut Mi-Mes T scap	CEv
<i>Cymbalaria muralis</i> P.Gaertn., B.Mey. & Scherb. 1800	v-a Mes-Mac SH herb	MSm
<i>Kickxia spuria</i> (L.) Dumort. 1827	a Mes-Mac ST herb	SAt
<i>Linaria vulgaris</i> Mill. 1768	a-aut Mes-Meg H scap	CEv
<i>Odontites vulgaris</i> Moench 1794	v-aut Mes-Mac dec ep SemiparT scap	CEv
<i>Orobanche lutea</i> Baumg. 1816	v Mes-Mac Par G	PSs
<i>Verbascum blattaria</i> L. 1753	v-a Mac-Alt H scap semiros bienn/T scap semiros	EAs
<i>Verbascum chaixii</i> Vill. 1779	a Mac-Meg H scap semiros	MSm
<i>Verbascum phlomoides</i> L. 1753	a Mac-Alt H scap semiros bienn	PSs
<i>Veronica anagallis-aquatica</i> L. 1753	v-aut Mes-Meg H scap	Hol
<i>Veronica arvensis</i> L. 1753	v Mi-Mes T scap/H scap bienn	CEv
<i>Veronica chamaedrys</i> L. 1753	v-a Mi-Mes H scap	CEv
<i>Veronica hederifolia</i> L. 1753	v Mes T caesp	CEv
<i>Veronica persica</i> Poir. 1808	v-a Mes-Mac T caesp/H caesp bienn	Adv
Bignoniaceae Juss. 1789		
<i>Catalpa bignonioides</i> Walter 1788	fo dec Mes P scap	Orn
Plantaginaceae Juss. 1789		
<i>Plantago altissima</i> L. 1762	a-aut Mac-Meg H ros	MSm
<i>Plantago lanceolata</i> L. 1753	a Mi-Meg H ros	EAs
<i>Plantago major</i> L. 1753	a Mes-Meg H ros	EAs
<i>Plantago media</i> L. 1753	a Mes-Meg H ros	EAs
Verbenaceae J. St.-Hil. 1805		

Taxa	Life form	Areal type
<i>Verbena officinalis</i> L. 1753	a Mes-Meg H scap	Cos
Lamiaceae Martinov 1820		
<i>Ajuga chamaepitys</i> (L.) Schreb. 1774	v-a Mes T scap rept	SAt
<i>Ajuga genevensis</i> L. 1753	a Mi-Mes H semiros	EAs
<i>Ajuga reptans</i> L. 1753	a Mes H rept	CEv
<i>Ballota nigra</i> L. 1753	a Meg H scap	PSs
<i>Clinopodium vulgare</i> L. 1753	a Mes-Meg H scap	Hol
<i>Glechoma hederacea</i> L. 1753	v-a Mes-Mac H rept	EAs
<i>Lamium amplexicaule</i> L. 1753	v Mes T scap	EAs
<i>Lamium purpureum</i> L. 1753	v-aut Mes T scap	CEv
<i>Leonurus cardiaca</i> L. 1753	a Mac-Alt H scap/G rhiz	EAs
<i>Lycopus europaeus</i> L. 1753	a Mac-Alt H scap/G rhiz	EAs
<i>Lycopus exaltatus</i> L.f. 1782	a Mac-Alt H scap/G rhiz	EAs
<i>Marrubium vulgare</i> L. 1753	a Mac H scap	EAs
<i>Mentha aquatica</i> L. 1753	rhiz emer HydG	EAs
<i>Mentha longifolia</i> (L.) L. 1756	a Mes-Meg H scap	CEv
<i>Mentha pulegium</i> L. 1753	a Mi-Mes H scap	CEv
<i>Mentha spicata</i> L. 1753	a Mes-Meg H scap/G rhiz	CEv
<i>Nepeta cataria</i> L. 1753	a Mac-Meg H scap/G rhiz	PSs
<i>Prunella vulgaris</i> L. 1753	a Mi-Mes H scap semiros	EAs
<i>Salvia glutinosa</i> L. 1753	a-aut Mac-Meg H scap	CEv
<i>Salvia nemorosa</i> L. 1762	v-a Mes-Mac H scap/G rhiz	PSs
<i>Salvia verticillata</i> L. 1753	a Mes-Meg H scap	PSs
<i>Scutellaria hastifolia</i> L. 1753	v-a Mes H scap/G rhiz	PSs
<i>Stachys annua</i> (L.) L. 1763	a-aut Mes-Mac T scap	PSs
<i>Stachys germanica</i> L. 1753	a Meg H scap	PSs
<i>Stachys palustris</i> L. 1753	a Mac-Alt G rhiz	Hol
<i>Teucrium chamaedrys</i> L. 1753	v-a Mes-Mac fo dec Ch suffr rept	PSs
<i>Thymus pulegioides</i> L. 1753 subsp. <i>pannonicus</i> (All.) Kerguélen 1993	v-a Mes-Mac fo dec Ch herb caesp	CEv
Liliopsida Batsch 1802		
Butomaceae Mirb. 1804		
<i>Butomus umbellatus</i> L. 1753	v-a Alt G rhiz	EAs
Hydrocharitaceae Juss. 1789		
<i>Elodea nuttallii</i> (Planch.) H.St.John 1920	er sbm HydG	Adv
<i>Hydrocharis morsus-ranae</i> L. 1753	stl nat HydG	EAs
<i>Stratiotes aloides</i> L. 1753	stl sbm HydG	CEv
Alismataceae Vent. 1799		
<i>Alisma plantago-aquatica</i> L. 1753	rhiz emer HydG	Cos
Potamogetonaceae Bercht. & J. Presl 1823		
<i>Potamogeton crispus</i> L. 1753	rhiz sbm HydG	Cos
<i>Potamogeton perfoliatus</i> L. 1753	rhiz nat HydG	Cos
Lemnaceae Gray 1821		
<i>Lemna gibba</i> L. 1753	er nat HydT	Cos
<i>Lemna minor</i> L. 1753	er nat HydT	Cos
<i>Lemna trisulca</i> L. 1753	er sbm HydT	Cos
<i>Spirodela polyrrhiza</i> (L.) Schleid. 1839	er nat HydT	Cos
Liliaceae Juss. 1789		
<i>Gagea pratensis</i> (Pers.) Dumort. 1827	v Mi-Mes G bulb	CEv
Iridaceae Juss. 1789		
<i>Iris × germanica</i> L. 1753	v Mac-Meg G rhiz	MSm
<i>Iris pseudacorus</i> L. 1753	rhiz emer HydG	CEv

Taxa	Life form	Areal type
Hyacinthaceae Batsch ex Borkh. 1797		
<i>Leopoldia comosa</i> (L.) Parl. 1847	v-a Mes-Meg G bulb	Msm
<i>Muscari neglectum</i> Guss. ex Ten. 1842	v Mes G bulb	Msm
<i>Ornithogalum refractum</i> Kit. ex Schldl. 1814	v Mi G bulb	PSs
<i>Ornithogalum umbellatum</i> L. 1753	v Mes G bulb	CEv
Agavaceae Dumort. 1829		
<i>Yucca filamentosa</i> L. 1753	fo semp N P scap	Orn
Alliaceae Borkh. 1797		
<i>Allium scorodoprasum</i> L. 1753	v-a Mac-Meg G bulb	CEv
<i>Allium sphaerocephalum</i> L. 1753	v-a Mac-Meg G bulb	PSs
Amaryllidaceae J. St.-Hil. 1805		
<i>Narcissus pseudonarcissus</i> L. 1753	v Mes G bulb	Adv
Asparagaceae Juss. 1789		
<i>Asparagus officinalis</i> L. 1753	v-a Mac-Alt G rhiz	PSs
Commelinaceae Mirb. 1804		
<i>Commelina communis</i> L. 1753	a Mes-Meg H rept	Adv
Juncaceae Juss. 1789		
<i>Juncus articulatus</i> L. 1753	a Mes-Meg H scap/G rhiz	Hol
<i>Juncus compressus</i> Jacq. 1762	v-a Mes G rhiz caesp	EAs
<i>Juncus gerardii</i> Loisel. 1809	v-a Mes G rhiz caesp	Hol
Cyperaceae Juss. 1789		
<i>Bolboschoenus maritimus</i> (L.) Palla 1905	rhiz emer HydG	Cos
<i>Carex distans</i> L. 1759	v-a Mes-Meg H caesp/G rhiz caesp	EAs
<i>Carex divisa</i> Huds. 1762	v-a Mes-Meg G rhiz	EAs
<i>Carex hirta</i> L. 1753	a Mes-Meg G rhiz caesp	EAs
<i>Carex melanostachya</i> M.Bieb. ex Willd. 1805	v-a Mac G rhiz	PSs
<i>Carex praecox</i> Schreb. 1771	v Mes G rhiz	EAs
<i>Carex riparia</i> Curtis 1783	v-a Mac-Alt G rhiz	Hol
<i>Carex spicata</i> Huds. 1762	v-a Mes-Meg H caesp	CEv
<i>Carex vulpina</i> L. 1753	v-a Mac-Meg H caesp	EAs
<i>Cyperus fuscus</i> L. 1753	a Mi-Mac T scap	EAs
<i>Schoenoplectus lacustris</i> (L.) Palla 1888	a-aut Meg-Alt G rhiz	Cos
Sparganiaceae Hanin 1811		
<i>Sparganium erectum</i> L. 1753	rhiz emer HydG	EAs
Typhaceae Juss. 1789		
<i>Typha angustifolia</i> L. 1753	rhiz emer HydG	Hol
<i>Typha latifolia</i> L. 1753	rhiz emer HydG	Cos
Poaceae Barnhart 1895		
<i>Agrostis stolonifera</i> L. 1753	a Mes-Alt G rhiz	EAs
<i>Alopecurus aequalis</i> Sobol. 1799	v-a Mes T caesp	EAs
<i>Alopecurus pratensis</i> L. 1753	v Mes-Mac G rhiz	EAs
<i>Arrhenatherum elatius</i> (L.) P.Beauv. ex J.Presl & C.Presl. 1819	a Mac-Alt H caesp	CEv
<i>Avena fatua</i> L. 1753	a Mac-Alt T scap	EAs
<i>Avena sativa</i> L. 1753	a Mac-Alt T scap	Orn
<i>Bothriochloa ischaemum</i> (L.) Keng 1936	a Mes-Mac H caesp	PSs
<i>Brachypodium pinnatum</i> (L.) P.Beauv. 1812	a Mac-Meg H scap	EAs
<i>Bromus hordeaceus</i> L. 1753	v-a Mac-Meg T caesp	Msm
<i>Bromus inermis</i> Leyss. 1761	a Mac-Alt H scap/G rhiz	EAs
<i>Bromus squarrosus</i> L. 1753	a Mes-Meg T scap	Msm
<i>Bromus sterilis</i> L. 1753	v-a Mac T caesp	EAs

Taxa	Life form	Areal type
<i>Bromus tectorum</i> L. 1753	v-a Mes-Meg T caesp	EAs
<i>Calamagrostis epigejos</i> (L.) Roth 1788	a Meg-Alt G rhiz	EAs
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i> (L.) Pers. 1805	a Mes-Mac G rhiz	Cos
<i>Dactylis glomerata</i> L. 1753	a Meg H caesp	EAs
<i>Dasypyrum villosum</i> (L.) Borbás 1896	v Mac-Meg T scap	Adv
<i>Digitaria ciliaris</i> (Retz.) Koeler 1802	a Mes T rept	Cos
<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i> (L.) P.Beauv. 1812	a Meg-Alt T caesp	Cos
<i>Echinochloa oryzoides</i> (Ard.) Fritsch 1891	a Meg-Alt T scap	Adv
<i>Elymus repens</i> (L.) Gould 1947	v-a Mac-Alt G rhiz	EAs
<i>Eragrostis minor</i> Host 1827	v-a Mes-Mac T caesp	Hol
<i>Festuca arundinacea</i> Schreb. 1771	a Meg-Alt H caesp	EAs
<i>Festuca ovina</i> L. 1753	v-a Mes-Mac H caesp	EAs
<i>Festuca pratensis</i> Huds. 1762	a Meg-Alt H caesp	EAs
<i>Glyceria maxima</i> (Hartm.) Holmb. 1919	rhiz emer HydG	Hol
<i>Hordeum distichon</i> L. 1753	v-a Mac-Meg T scap	Orn
<i>Hordeum murinum</i> L. 1753	v-a Mes T caesp	Msm
<i>Koeleria macrantha</i> (Ledeb.) Schult. 1824	v-a Mes-Mac H caesp	Hol
<i>Lolium multiflorum</i> Lam. 1788	v-a Mac-Meg T caesp/H caesp bienn	Msm
<i>Lolium perenne</i> L. 1753	v-a Mac-Meg H caesp	CEv
<i>Panicum capillare</i> L. 1753	a Mac T caesp	Adv
<i>Phalaris arundinacea</i> L. 1753	a Meg-Alt G rhiz	Hol
<i>Phragmites australis</i> (Cav.) Trin. ex Steud. 1841	rhiz emer HydG	Cos
<i>Poa annua</i> L. 1753	v-aut Mi-Mes T caesp/H caesp bienn/G rhiz caesp	Cos
<i>Poa bulbosa</i> L. 1753	a Mes-Meg H caesp	EAs
<i>Poa pratensis</i> L. 1753	v-a Mes-Meg H caesp/G rhiz caesp	Hol
<i>Poa trivialis</i> L. 1753	a Mes-Meg H caesp	EAs
<i>Puccinellia distans</i> (Jacq.) Parl. 1850	a Mes-Meg H caesp	EAs
<i>Sclerochloa dura</i> (L.) P.Beauv. 1812	v-a Mi-Mes T caesp	Msm
<i>Setaria pumila</i> (Poir.) Roem. & Schult. 1817	a Mes-Mac T rept	EAs
<i>Setaria verticillata</i> (L.) P.Beauv. 1812	a Mac-Meg T scap	Cos
<i>Setaria viridis</i> (L.) P.Beauv. 1812	a Mes-Mac T rept	EAs
<i>Sorghum halepense</i> (L.) Pers. 1805	a Meg-Alt G rhiz	Cos
<i>Triticum aestivum</i> L. 1753	v-a Meg-Alt T scap	Adv

Legend: Life form: a - summerly, ac - needle-leaved, Alt - tall, aut - autumnal, bienn - biannual, bulb - bulbous, caesp - caespitose, Ch - Chamaephytes, dec - deciduous, emer - emerged, er (errantia) - non root-bud plant, fo - foliose, G - Geophytes, H - Hemicryptophytes, herb - herbaceous, Hyd - Hydrophytes, lig - ligneous, Mac (Macro) - big/tall/long, Meg (Mega) - big, large, Mes (Meso) - intermediate, Mi (Micro) - small/low, N (nano) - dwarf, nat - natant, floating, P - Phanerophytes, Par - parasitophytes, rad (radicantia) - root-bud plant, rept - reptant, rhiz - rhizomatous, ros - rosulate, S - Scandentophytes, sbm - submerged, scap - scapose, Semipar - Semiparasitophytes, semiros - semirosulate, semp - evergreen, stl - stoloniferous, suffr - suffruticose, succ - succulent, T - therophytes, tub - tuberous, v - vernal; Areal type: Adv - Adventitious, CEv - Central European, Cos - Cosmopolitan, EAs - Euroasian, Hol - Holarctic, Msm - Mediterranean-Submediterranean, Orn - Ornamental, PSs - Pontic-South Siberian, SAt - Subatlantic.